

Propagation of measurement error in opinion dynamics models: The case of the Deffuant model

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 30 July 2021

Received in revised form 28 June 2022

Available online 5 September 2022

Dataset link: https://github.com/just-a-normal-dino/error_propagation_deffuant/blob/main/deffuant_sensitivity_for_publication3.ipynb

Keywords:

Opinion dynamics
Empirical validation
Deffuant model
Measurement error
Prediction
Psychometrics

ABSTRACT

Opinion dynamics models have an enormous potential for studying current phenomena such as vaccine hesitancy or diffusion of fake news. Unfortunately, to date, most of the models have little to no empirical validation. One major problem in testing these models against real-world data relates to the difficulties in measuring opinions in ways that map directly to representations in models. Indeed, measuring opinions is a complex process and presents more types of measurement error than just classical random noise. Thus, it is crucial to know how these different error types may affect the model's predictions. In this work, we analyze this relationship in the Deffuant model as an example. Starting from the psychometrics literature, we first discuss how opinion measurements are affected by three types of errors: random noise, binning, and distortions (i.e. uneven intervals between scale points). While the first two are known to most of the scientific community, the third one is mostly unknown outside psychometrics. Because of that, we highlight the nature and peculiarities of each of these measurement errors. By simulating these types of error, we show that the Deffuant model is robust to binning but not to noise and distortions. Indeed, if a scale has 4 or more points (like most self-report scales), binning has almost no effect on the final predictions. However, prediction error increases almost linearly with random noise, up to a maximum error of 40%. After reaching this value, increasing the amount of noise does not worsen the prediction. Distortions are most problematic, reaching a maximum prediction error of 80%. Error propagation is already established in other fields, such as statistics and engineering. We believe its application in opinion dynamics will contribute to the expansion and development of this field. Indeed, as we show here, it allows researchers to test models' reliability and prediction quality even before testing the model against real world data.

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1. Introduction

Opinion dynamics is a sub-field of agent-based modeling focused on people's opinions [1,2]. Models from this field are good candidates for better understanding pressing social problems, such as vaccine hesitancy or the spread of fake news. Some experiments have been conducted testing the core principles of these models [3,4], however, current opinion

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dynamics models are rarely used with real world data [1,5–7]. This means that, for several models, it is not possible to tell if a model will be accurate or not in its predictions.

Indeed, since 2009 different articles and reviews exhorted researchers to validate their model against real-world data [1,2,8,9]. Probably because of that, recently, some projects aimed at achieving this goal received substantial funding from different agencies [10,11]. Thus, we expect that in the following years more and more effort will be dedicated in validating opinion dynamics models.

One of the biggest issues in bridging this gap between models and data, lays in the fact that measuring opinions is a complex process. Indeed, physical measurements rely on well-defined units of measurements, while nothing similar exists for measuring opinions [12,13]. Notice that this does not mean that it is not possible to make such a measurement. Indeed, the field of psychometrics has developed theory, methodology and standards just for this type of task [14–16]. However, the types of measurement error that affect opinions are not the same as those that affect physical measurements.

In this work, we study how measurement errors can propagate in the model resulting in uncertainty on the final prediction. Similar procedures are already well established in fields like statistics and physics under the name of propagation of error (or propagation of uncertainty) [17]. Thus, we believe they will strongly help the field of opinion dynamics to get closer and closer to estimating reliability of the models' predictions.

We decided to test our error propagation method on the well-established Deffuant model. We choose this model both because its properties are well known in the field and for its simplicity [1,18]. Notice, however, that the same analysis could be carried also on other models. Indeed, our main goal with this work is not to study the Deffuant model in detail, but just to use it as an example for the process of error propagation in opinion dynamics models.

In the next section, we discuss how psychometric theory introduces three types of measurement errors. In the method section, we discuss how we simulated each one of them and estimated their effect. In the analysis section we show, via simulations, how each type of measurement error impacts the Deffuant model's predictions. Finally, in the discussion, we clarify the implications of these results and discuss some future perspectives.

2. Psychometric measurements

2.1. A review of measurement errors

Before testing the Deffuant model against measurement errors, it is important to clarify the effects that influence a measurement. A common approach in the so-called “hard sciences” is to suppose the existence of a true value v to be measured [19,20]. This value is usually considered to belong to the real numbers. As the existence of v is a controversial assumption in psychology, in the next sub-section we will better discuss this hypothesis and how the following analysis can be adapted to a case in which no real value exists. However, for simplicity, we start by assuming the existence of such a value. Furthermore, we start by analyzing each type of noise independently.

When we perform a measurement $m(v)$ affected by random noise we obtain as result:

$$m(v) = v + r \quad (1)$$

Where r is a randomly distributed variable representing the noise. It is also commonly supposed that r has a normal (also known as “Gaussian”) distribution of mean zero and a standard deviation σ [19]. Thus σ can be used as a measurement of the noise's intensity.

When the measurement instrument has a relatively small number of levels it is common to include a discretization (or quantization) error [21]. For example, an instrument measuring voltage may be able to display either 5 or 6 V, but not the values in between. Similarly, a 10-point self-report measure of political opinion would be able to distinguish between a person with opinion 1 to a person with opinion 2, but not between people within this range. Meaning that a person with opinion 1.6 will probably receive a score of 2, making this value indistinguishable from the score of participant with opinion 1.9. In general, we will write this type of measurements as:

$$m(v) = \text{bin}(v) \quad (2)$$

Where $\text{bin}()$ is a rounding-like function, such as round . For example, we can suppose that v is a number between 0 and 1 and that we are measuring it on an 11-point scale from 0 to 10. Then, the bin function will take the form of $\text{bin}(v) = \text{round}(10 * v)$.

Up to now, we were able to draw some parallel with measurements in physics. However, there is another fundamental effect which is unique to measurement of variables such as opinions. Indeed, in physics, measurements are performed in specific units (e.g. meters or feet for measuring distance). Unfortunately, in psychometrics, there is no thing such as a unit of opinion. This does not mean that we will not be able to measure opinions. Indeed, this is almost a standard procedure in the literature. However, our measurement will not be linear with respect to the true value [12,22,23] even if we suppose that such a true value exists. Thus, we can represent the measurement process as:

$$m(v) = h(v) \quad (3)$$

Where $h()$ is a monotonic function, which, in general will be non-linear. Where a function f is considered to be linear if for every scalar α we have $f(\alpha v) = \alpha f(v)$.

These non-linear kinds of measurement are often referred as “ordinal measurements” [12] as they preserve order. Indeed, if there is an order in the true values, such as $v_1 \leq v_2$ then the same order is preserved in the measurement: $h(v_1) \leq h(v_2)$.

However, notice that this kind of measurement does not preserve distance and proportions. For example, if $v_2 = 2v_1$ then in standard measurement we would expect also $m(v_2) = 2m(v_1)$. However, since h is a non-linear function, this relationship would not be true.

Because of this feature, these kinds of scales have been often graphically represented as a ruler with uneven spacing between the ticks. With such a ruler, we could say that an object of length 6 is longer than an object of length 3, but not that it is actually twice as long.

Many people here may be confused from the fact that $2 * 3 = 6$, thus, they think that one object should be twice as long as the other. However, to reason correctly, we should differentiate between the object itself (or true value) and its measurement in this distorted scale. Indeed, in this case we can say that one measurement is twice the other, even if this relationship does not exist between the objects. In formula: $m(v_2) = 2m(v_1)$ but $v_2 \neq 2v_1$.

Another small difference between measuring opinions and measurement in physics is that psychometric scales are usually based on several items (i.e. questions). This means that a single measurement $m(v)$ is usually obtained by combining responses to several items from the same person. However, for simplicity, here we will just focus on the scale measurement errors, without analyzing how such a scale has been obtained.

While the first two types of errors are well known even in classical physics, the problem of distortions become particularly relevant with psychometric measurements. Also because of this, there are many studies showing how these distortions may affect standard procedures in psychological measurement, such as in t-test and ANOVA procedures [24–27]. However, to our knowledge, almost nothing is known on how they may impact agent-based modeling.

2.2. On the existence of the true value

In our argument so far we have assumed the existence of a true value, similarly to classical physics. This assumption has already been discarded in quantum physics, where due to Heisenberg uncertainty principle it is not possible to identify a true value for measurements such as position or speed [28,29].

Something similar happens also in psychometrics where we cannot measure v but only $h(v)$ [12]. Furthermore, h is an unknown function. This means that we cannot measure it and, even if we try to use another measurement, we will only end up with another unknown transformation. For example, two measurements of the same value v on two different scales will result in $h_1(v)$ and $h_2(v)$. Thus, even by adding more measurements, the system will remain underdetermined, and we would not be able to find the true value of v or, equivalently, the shape of h .

This has brought many to the conclusion that a true value may not even exist as a numerically quantifiable internal construct [30]. Others, instead, suppose its existence and that it should be theoretically possible to obtain it through procedures based on a theory called additive conjoint theory [12,31]. In both cases, researchers agree that is practically impossible to extract a true value from most of the available data [32,33]. Because of this, some models have even developed already in their structure the impossibility of perceiving or expressing an accurate value [34]

However, the absence of a true value does not mean that we cannot use the measurement model provided in our previous equations. Indeed, while we cannot compare scales to a true value, we can still compare scales to an arbitrary reference scale without any additional claims about its properties.

For example, for measuring political opinion we could use the “12 Item Social and Economic Conservatism Scale” (SECS) [35]. Alternatively, we can choose any other scale from the literature or even create our own scale, as long as it is measuring the right construct (in this case “political opinion”). This is similar to the situation in physics, where we can choose either meters or feet, or any other unit as long as it is a good measurement of distance.

Thus, in the previous equations we can just replace the true value v with v_r , the value on a reference scale. Notice also that while the previous assumption was extremely demanding, the new assumption is always met in practice. Indeed, initially we assumed the existence of a true value, while now we just assume that we can generate a scale. This process is routinely done in psychology.

Notice also that this choice of the reference scale is useful also for identifying the transformation function h . Indeed, while we cannot measure the relationship between a scale and the true value (as it will require to know the true value) we can always compare two scales.

For example, in Fig. 1 we see the comparison of two scales of trust in science. Each one has been obtained averaging three questions on trust in science from the Wellcome Global Monitor [36]. This kind of flexible item selection is common in social sciences. Since the original survey contained only five questions on this topic the two scales have one of the three items in common.

From the plot, we can see that people that scored 6 on scale 1 also scored an average of 6 on scale 2. However, people who scored 10 on scale 1 scored on average 7 on scale 2. Thus, this plot practically shows us that we can choose a reference scale (scale 1) and compare it to another one (scale 2). Furthermore, it also graphically shows us the three errors we just discussed. Indeed, the error bar shows the effect of random noise, while the fact that points do not follow a linear behavior (orange dashed line) shows us the effect of distortions. Finally, the fact that we have only 10 points (from a score of 3 to 12) shows us the fact that both scales have only a few levels (i.e. binning) instead of being a continuous variable.

Fig. 1. Average score on scale 2 versus the score on scale 1. The dashed line shows the ideal linear behavior. The size of the error bar is due to random noise and the non-linearity shows us the effect of distortions.

3. Method

In this work we want to show how we can perform error propagation on the Deffuant model. Specifically, we want to observe how strongly the set of the final opinions will be distorted by different types of error.

3.1. The Deffuant model and parameters

As mentioned before, the Deffuant model [18] is a simple model which in general leads to a simple dynamic behavior. Every agent's opinion is represented as a real number between 0 and 1. In this way, it is possible to calculate the distance between their opinions. The parameter ε represents the maximum possible distance of interaction. Indeed, if agent's distance is higher than ε they will not be able to interact. Otherwise, they will move towards the average opinion. The amount of movement is proportional to the parameter μ and it follows the formula:

$$o_i(t+1) = (1-\mu)o_i(t) + \mu o_j(t) \quad (4)$$

Where $o_i(t)$ is the opinion of agent i at time t .

For the dynamic evolution of the system, couples of agents are randomly chosen at every round. Here we use T to denote the maximum number of rounds.

Usually studies on the Deffuant model focus on its convergence state. However, similarly to most opinion dynamics models, the Deffuant model converges to very unrealistic distributions. Indeed, when the model has converged, all the people share the same N opinions, where N is roughly $1/\varepsilon$. Thus, studying the model's predictions at convergence is another approach which may be quite unrealistic.

Because of that, here we study the models predictions for shorter time (i.e. before convergence). Indeed, before convergence, the opinion distribution still resembles possible shapes of real-world data making the analysis closer to more realistic scenarios.¹ Furthermore, if the dynamics formalized in the model are similar to those experienced by real-world people, then the predictions should also be valid in shorter time frames. Another point in favor of this approach, is that models in complex systems (e.g. in meteorology) are precise only for short time dynamics. Indeed, they become more and more imprecise as they try to forecast further in the future [38]. Because of this, we did not focus on the predictions of the converged model, but on the predictions at shorter time intervals. Furthermore, as the convergence does not only depend on T but also on the number of agents, we usually represent time using $T_r = \frac{T}{N_a}$, where N_a is the number of agents.

Besides ε , μ and T_r there is another "parameter" which is often not discussed in the literature: the initial distribution. Indeed, a common assumption is to start simulations using a uniform distribution. However, this is not a good representation of real-world opinion distributions, which can have more complex shapes and properties that can affect the model dynamics [9]. Thus, we simulated distributions generated by using a third order interpolation of 4 randomly generated numbers. Two examples of these distributions are shown in Fig. 1. Notice here that due to the constraints on the curve, it

¹ Notice that even if some evidence has been found that people tend to move towards the opinion value of the person they are interacting with [37] the Deffuant model may still not represent real dynamics even for shorter time ranges.

Distribution functions

Fig. 2. Two examples of distributions used to seed the model.

may pass rather far away from the points that should be interpolated. However, this is not a problem. Indeed, the goal of this algorithm is not to produce a good fit of the random points, but to produce random curves (see Fig. 2). Despite not being included in the original article from Deffuant and Weisbuch, another part of the system which is often studied is the network topology [39]. However, since our analysis already depends on several parameters, we choose to not introduce an extra one leaving this study for possible future works. Thus, all the dynamic behavior we will discuss in the following will be on a fully-connected network (i.e. everyone can interact with everyone else, subject to the bounded confidence interval ε).

3.2. Management of the parameter space

Despite the Deffuant model being one of the simplest models in the opinion dynamics literature, we can see that our analysis has to deal with several parameters (this is one of the main reasons of why as example, we choose one of the simplest and best known models available). Because of this, a full exploration of the parameters space is not feasible. A solution used in some works consists in fixing T , N_a , ε and μ to some specific values for the entire analysis [39]. Another common approach in these cases is the so called OFAT method (one factor at a time) [40]. This method consists in fixing all the parameter to a set of chosen values and varying only one of them at a time. Once the exploration of that parameter has been completed, it is fixed to its original value and a new parameter is explored.

Since we want our results to be as general as possible, we used a mixed method. Indeed, as we will discuss in the next section, the prediction error appears to be independent on T_r and N_a . Because of that, the analysis will be carried out with $N_a = 200$ and $T_r = 1$. Since the other parameters have an effect on the prediction error, we decided to randomize them for each run. Specifically, we randomly choose ε and μ between 0 and 0.5 as these are the standard extremes used for analyzing the Deffuant model. Instead, the distribution curve is initialized each time in the way discussed in the previous section. Furthermore, we also set all the error sources to zero, besides the one under analysis.

For example, if we are studying the effect of binning, we will set the scale to a specific value (e.g. a 10-point scale) and set the noise and distortions to 0. Then, we will randomly choose ε , μ and the distribution curve and run the simulation. We will then compare this prediction with the prediction of a model having exactly the same parameters but no measurement error (i.e. maximal number of bins). This difference will be used to calculate the error. Since there are several random parameters in the simulation, we will repeat this process many times, by selecting again a 10-point scale, but new random values of ε , μ and the distribution curve. Thus, we will collect an entire set of prediction errors for a single value of measurement error (e.g. 10 bins).

3.3. Measurement of error and distortions

We calculated the prediction error by using Theil's inequality coefficient [41]. This value has been employed to measure how similar two predictions are. Indeed, for two predictions X and Y it can be calculated as:

$$E(X, Y) = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_i (x_i - y_i)^2}}{(\sqrt{\sum_i x_i^2} + \sqrt{\sum_i y_i^2})} \quad (5)$$

Where x_i is the opinion of person i in prediction X . Notice that this value is always between 0 and 1. The value 0 represents the case of perfect prediction (i.e. $x_i = y_i$) while 1 represents the case of maximum error. This is achieved if either X or Y is constantly zero.

Notice here how we could define multiple types of error depending on what we want to predict or what we want to be accurate about. Indeed, in this specific case, we are measuring the opinion distance on the same agent for two runs. However, alternative approaches are possible. For example, one may want to check only that the overall distribution is correct without caring about the opinion of the single agent. In some analysis or models, instead, we may want to make sure that only a certain class of agents, or only one part of the opinion space is accurate. For example, when studying vaccination, one may focus on how reliable the model is at distinguishing between pro- and anti-vaccination opinions, with little interest in within group variations.

In our study, we choose this definition of the error, as we want to test the model in the most stringent case. Furthermore, this approach is robust to changing the binning criteria.

In our analysis X is the prediction we obtained from the simulation without measurement errors, while Y is the prediction obtained by including the measurement error under analysis (e.g. using only 5 bins in the opinion scale). All the other parameters used to produce X and Y are exactly the same. This means that to generate X and Y we run the Deffuant model using the same parameters (initial distribution, T_r , N_a , ε and μ). The only difference is that to produce Y we also added a measurement error before running the model. Thus $E(X, Y)$ represents the prediction error we would observe comparing two scales: one with measurement error and another without.

As reference scale we chose a 101-point one as precision of self-report measures rarely exceeds this. Indeed, while any scale could be used as a reference, for this study we selected one that would be similar to a maximally precise psychometric measurement under ideal conditions to then simulate what happens as precision is decreased.

Regarding the simulations, we chose not to limit the precision of the model dynamics. Meaning that only the initial values of seeded data would be represented on the scale levels, but not the intermediate dynamics or final level. To provide an example, we can consider having an opinion scale with only two points. Thus, the model would be seeded with all agents either having an initial opinion of 0 or 1. However, during the simulation, they will still follow the Deffuant dynamics without being limited to these two values (e.g. they could move to 0.6 even if this is not a point on the initial scale). These final values will be then used to calculate Theil's coefficient. In this way, we were able to run the Deffuant model without having to add any new rule to deal with discretized data.

As we discussed, the amount of binning is quantified by the number of points on the measurement scale. The amount of random noise, instead, is quantified by σ , the standard deviation of the normally distributed noise variable. Finally, distortions are quantified by the deviation from the linear behavior:

$$D(X, h) = \frac{\sum_i |x_i - h(x_i)|}{\sum_i x_i} \quad (6)$$

Where x_i is the set of values on the reference scale (i.e. the position of the bins) and $h(x_i)$ are the equivalent values on the measurement scale. Similarly to the Theil's coefficient, D ranges between 0 and 1. Specifically, 0 would be the case of perfect linearity, while 1 would be the case of maximum non-linearity (e.g. when $h(x_i) = 0$ for every x_i or when $h(x_i) = 1$ for every x_i).

4. Analysis

4.1. Intrinsic stochastic error

Before studying how different measurement error affect the prediction error, we should first notice that the Deffuant model is affected by random variations. An extremely simple example would be to make predictions after a single step. In the first run of the model, we could have that person 1 and person 10 are randomly chosen for the interaction. However, if we repeat the same configuration for a second run, we could choose a different couple. This means that predictions would be different even without introducing any measurement error. We refer to this effect as the "intrinsic stochastic error".

We measured the intrinsic stochastic error by randomizing N_a between 100 and 1000, T_r between 0.1 and 5, ε and μ between 0 and 0.5. We observed that the average error to be 0.054 with a standard deviation of 0.038.

As we can see from Fig. 3, the intrinsic stochastic error is not dependent on T_r and N_a . This is the reason why for further analysis these two parameters will be fixed to $T_r = 1$ and $N_a = 200$. We choose these two values as they are small enough for efficient computation.

Regarding ε , we observe that it influences the prediction error only for $\varepsilon < 0.1$, while above this value the error keeps oscillating around its mean value. Instead, regarding μ the error keeps increasing as this value increases. It is important to notice that μ has a direct influence on how much each agent will move during the simulation. Thus, it makes sense that the higher this value the bigger the error will be in the final prediction. Similarly, ε has an indirect effect on the agents movement. Indeed, for very small ε agents will be able to interact only with their direct neighbors.

Parameter's effect on the prediction error

Fig. 3. Prediction error depending on different parameters. Black lines represents the maximum and minimum errors. Red dashed line represents the intrinsic stochastic error. The purple dot represents the average error value, while the error bar represents the standard deviation of the error.

4.2. The effect of random noise

The first measurement error that we analyze is the random noise. As mentioned before, this is usually modeled as normally distributed with mean of 0 and a standard deviation of σ . As measurement errors affect only the initial data, it is interesting to see what its effect on the initial distribution is.

To better understand how this noise works, we can think of an example in which every agent on the reference scale has an opinion of 0.5. If now we introduce the randomly distributed noise, we will have that the mean opinion on the new scale will still be 0.5, however agents' opinions are spread around this value following a normal distribution with a standard deviation of σ .

If the initial distribution is not just a single peak, but a more complex shape, we can still use the previous procedure to see where agents will be. Indeed, also in this case, all agents which initially were in 0.5 will be randomly distributed around this value. All the agents which were in 0.6 will be randomly distributed around 0.6, and so on for each position.

Mathematically, this operation is called convolution [42] and it is represented as:

$$f_1(x) = f_0(x) * n(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_0(t)n(x - t)dt \tag{7}$$

Where f_0 is the initial distribution, f_1 the final one, n is the noise function and $*$ is the symbol of convolution.

Connecting this type of noise to convolution has the advantage that this mathematical operation has been intensively studied and its effect on other functions is well known. Indeed, convolving a function with a normally distributed one, has the effect of smoothening the first function. For example, in optics, a blurred image is modeled as the convolution of the high-quality image with a normally distributed function [43].

In Fig. 4 we can see the effect of the random noise on the prediction error. As expected for 0 noise, the prediction error is still close to the intrinsic stochastic error, which is the case of no measurement error. As the amount of noise

Fig. 4. Prediction error versus the amount of measurement noise measured in terms of σ . Black lines represent the maximum and minimum errors. Red dashed line represents the intrinsic stochastic error. The purple dot represents the average error value, the error bar represents the standard deviation of the error. The blue dashed line is the piecewise linear approximation.

increases, the prediction error keeps linearly increasing up to a value of roughly 0.4 for $\sigma = 0.5$. After this value of σ , the prediction error does not seem to increase anymore.

We can then approximate the noise with a piecewise linear function as:

$$\begin{cases} 0.05 + 0.70\sigma & \text{if } \sigma \leq 0.5 \\ 0.4 & \text{if } \sigma > 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Notice that while we analyzed the effects of noise up to $\sigma = 1$, usually in empirical data the amount of noise will be much smaller. For example, we can use the data used for producing Fig. 1 (i.e. from the Wellcome Global Monitor) to calculate that between the two scales there is a measurement noise of roughly 0.1. By substituting this value into the previous formula, we have that the average prediction error would be 0.085, which is a relatively small increase to the intrinsic stochastic error.

4.3. The effect of binning

The second effect we study is due to binning. This is a fundamental effect as measurements in psychometrics usually have a few levels, as opposed to measurements in physics which may easily have thousands or even millions of levels. Indeed, in psychometrics it is common to measure someone's opinion on a topic by asking one or a few questions. Each question is also usually limited to a few response options, typically ranging from 2 to 10. The answers from single questions are then combined to produce an overall score with increased number of levels [44]. As previously mentioned, the reference scale in our simulations has 101 levels, so it is interesting to analyze how prediction error changes as we decrease the number of levels on the new scale.

As we can see in Fig. 5, the error is almost constant for scales with 4 or more levels. Then the error has a very rapid increase below 4. The worst situation is, of course, the case of only 2 levels, which produces an average prediction error of 0.34.

This result is extremely positive for people intending to use the Deffuant model with real-world data. Indeed, most measurement items provide more than 3 levels, thus providing the minimum prediction error.

Notice also that in this specific case we do not provide a piecewise linear approximation as the prediction error is non-constant only in two points. Thus, it makes more sense to directly report their value, instead of providing an approximation. Thus, the prediction error for 2 and 3 levels is respectively 0.34 and 0.12.

This analysis shows also some kind of data-incompatibility between the Deffuant model and some other models. Indeed, literature in agent-based modeling is often interested in the difference between models [45]. One sub-class of models in opinion dynamics is based on binary states, such as in the voter model [46,47]. This means that this class of models is designed for dealing with opinions measured on 2-point scales. As showed, when the Deffuant model is used with this type of data it is affected by extremely high prediction uncertainty. Meaning that data which would be perfect for one model, would produce terrible results in another.

4.4. The effect of distortions

The final analysis regards the effect of distortions. As mentioned in the introduction, these non-linear transformations are unavoidable features of psychometric measures such as Likert-type scales which are the standard for measuring

Fig. 5. Prediction error versus the number of points in the scale. Black lines represent the maximum and minimum errors. Red dashed line represents the intrinsic stochastic error. The purple dot represents the average error value, the error bar represents the standard deviation of the error.

Fig. 6. Prediction error versus distortions. Black lines represent the maximum and minimum errors. Red dashed line represents the intrinsic stochastic error. The purple dot represents the average error value, the error bar represents the standard deviation of the error. The blue dashed line is the piecewise linear approximation.

opinions [44]. From Fig. 6 we can see that distortions up to 0.1 produce almost no increase in the prediction error. However, after this value, the prediction error starts rising almost linearly with the distortion value. This effect is so strong to reach an average prediction error higher than 0.8. Following this behavior, we approximated these data with the following piecewise linear function:

$$\begin{cases} 0.05 & \text{if } D \leq 0.1 \\ 0.8D - 0.03 & \text{if } D > 0.1 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

To have a better idea of how strong this effect may be in real-world data, we can use again the data from the Wellcome Global Monitor. Here we find a distortion value of 0.26, which leads to an average prediction error of 0.18. This is more than 3 times bigger than the intrinsic stochastic error.

To better understand this result, let us suppose two people decide independently to use the data from the Wellcome Global Monitor with the Deffuant model to predict trust in science. If one person uses scale 1 and the other uses scale 2, then their predictions will differ by an average of 0.18.

This represents an important factor for using real-world data with the Deffuant model. Indeed, while the noise and the number of levels have a quite limited effect on the prediction error, distortions may easily produce much higher prediction errors.

5. Conclusion

In this paper we showed how we can measure reliability of opinion dynamics models with error propagation. For doing this, we introduced the types of measurement errors that can affect opinion data and tested their effect on the predictions

of the Deffuant model. The model shows an intrinsic error of 0.054 which does not depend on the number of agents or running time. Instead, this value is weakly dependent on the two model's parameters ε and μ .

Regarding measurement errors, we observed that the model is independent on the number of levels of the scale if this number is above 3. However, if a scale with 3 or 2 levels is used the prediction error will quickly rise up to an average error of 0.34. As most scales have more than three bins (especially multi-items scales), binning is likely to have little effect on predictions. This also shows a type of data incompatibility between the Deffuant model and binary ones such as the voter model. Indeed, these models are designed to work with 2-points scales, where the Deffuant model will have extremely high prediction error.

Random noise and distortions, contrary to binning, may have a massive effect on the Deffuant model's prediction. Specifically, the prediction error is roughly linear with both effects. However, random noise reaches a maximum of 0.4 for $\sigma = 0.5$ and then stops increasing. Instead, distortions keep contributing to the prediction error up to an average error bigger than 0.8. Furthermore, by using values from scales obtained from the Wellcome Global Monitor, we found that here random noise produces a prediction error of 0.085 while distortion produces an error of 0.18. This means that researchers interested in using real-world data should be particularly careful about these two effects.

While in this article we focused on continuous-type models (e.g. the Deffuant or Hegselmann Krause models) alternatives exists which use discrete opinions [48], or a combinations of continuous and discrete [49], some of which have already compared with real-world data [50–56]. Since the error propagation method we explained could be applied to them as well, in future studies it would be interesting to explore also the stability of their results when fed with opinion data.

In this article, we started analyzing the propagation of measurement error in opinion dynamics models. Indeed, in the future, we may be able to use opinion dynamics models for tasks such as accurately identifying which countries may risk developing a strong increase in distrust towards vaccines [57]. Furthermore, these models could be implemented in policy-making for designing highly effective interventions.

However, to reach this ambitious goal, many more studies should focus on how to use real data with opinion dynamics models. Indeed, many aspects are still unknown. For example: will opinion dynamics models be able to precisely predict the future opinion distribution, or maybe only describe qualitative characteristics (e.g. polarization)? Could these models be used only with small groups or should they model entire populations? In the latter case, how big should the collected sample be to ensure reliable results?

Many of these questions are still unexplored in our field, and probably it will take some decades to develop clear standards on data and predictions. This is similar to linear modeling in psychology, where it took a very long time to develop the best practices for dealing with the data [24–27]. However, we believe that the joint efforts of our community will be able to develop innovative techniques for producing reliable predictions on some of the most pressing social issues (e.g. vaccine hesitancy and global warming).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dino Carpentras: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Michael Quayle:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Code is available at the link provided in the article https://github.com/just-a-normal-dino/error_propagation_deffuant/blob/main/deffuant_sensitivity_for_publication3.ipynb.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 891347 and from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. 802421).

Appendix. Supplementary material

The code used for generating the data can be found at:
https://github.com/just-a-normal-dino/error_propagation_deffuant/blob/main/deffuant_sensitivity_for_publication3.ipynb.

While the analysis of the model until convergence can be found at:
https://github.com/just-a-normal-dino/error_propagation_deffuant/blob/main/Supplementary%20material.pdf

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